

Workshop Report: Train-the-Trainer Session on Data Management Plans and RDMO – 30 June 2025

On June 30th 2025, DMP4NFDI conducted its first Train-the-Trainer (TtT) workshop on Data Management Plans (DMPs) and RDMO for the project use cases and a few other consortia who expressed a high level of interest. Following the developed TtT concept for DMPs and RDMO¹, the workshop was grounded on the Advanced-level training module for DMPs. The interactive workshop covered the differences between *Train-the-Trainer* and *regular* workshops, introduced the tailored TtT concept for DMPs and RDMO, explored DMPs vs. machine-actionable DMPs (maDMPs), included a live demonstration of RDMO, and provided practical guidance on didactic methods for effective knowledge transfer.

In three breakout sessions, participants engaged in a 20-minute group discussion focused on the creation of DMP templates tailored to the needs of their consortia. Participants with prior experience in developing DMP templates shared their approaches and compared them with others, highlighting both common practices and discipline-specific differences. For participants without prior experience in creating DMP templates, the discussion centered around the types of data generated or collected within their consortia, using DMP components to identify key elements relevant to their fields. The discussion results were presented in plenum, facilitating an overview around DMP practices within participating consortia. It also allowed an exchange of ideas for future DMP development to improve and streamline workflow processes. [Table 1](#) shows a summary of the group work results.

The gathered feedback showed a positive response to the first TtT workshop on DMPs and RDMO. The interactive elements and the opportunity to engage with other consortia was highlighted as particularly valuable. The breakout sessions were seen as a good forum for sharing experiences, and the prepared workshop materials were well received. The overall structure of the workshop was appreciated, with clear organisation, informative slides, and a well-structured roadmap. The inclusion of realistic scenarios in the live demo also resonated well with participants.

Several suggestions for improvement were also raised. Some attendees had expected more concrete guidance on how to create and deliver their own DMP workshops, including examples of structure, content, and available open educational resources. There was also a call for clarity around the practical application and benefits of the TtT concept. While the introductory RDMO content was useful for some, others found it too basic.

Participants recommended more didactic-focused training sessions in the future. Tailoring DMP and RDMO workshops to specific consortia was also suggested, as this could enhance perceived relevance and tool adoption. Feedback on the breakout session moderation was mixed: some appreciated having a moderator who could summarise group results, especially for those less comfortable presenting, while others preferred unmoderated discussions to encourage open exchange. Finally, it was proposed that feedback collection be moved to the end or after the session to allow more time for interaction during the workshop itself.

¹ Gonzalez Ocanto, M., Diederichs, K., Schönau, S., Wallace, D., & Windeck, J. (2025). DMP4NFDI Train-the-Trainer Concept on Data Management Plans and RDMO. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15771036>

Table 1. Summary results of breakout sessions

<p>Similarities</p>	<p>There is a shared awareness of the importance of DMPs, especially within central RDM service units.</p> <p>RDMO is commonly used across participating consortia and often already serves as a central integration point for other systems.</p> <p>The DFG checklist served some consortia as a basis for the creation of DMP templates.</p> <p>The need to motivate communities and contextualize DMPs for users was a recurring theme.</p> <p>Funders' requirements are a key driver for DMP adoption across consortia.</p>
<p>Differences</p>	<p>Use cases and implementations vary. E.g., NFDI4Culture uses DMPs as a decision tree for museums to select a collection management system; NFD4Earth, NFD4Cat, and NFD4Chem have different stages of DMP adoption and tool integration.</p> <p>Different RDMO clients are in use (e.g., hosted by DMP4NFDI vs. hosted directly by the consortium).</p> <p>Differences in data types (analog vs. digital), metadata standards, and repository choices (generic vs. discipline-specific).</p> <p>The structure and mandatory content of DMP templates differ across consortia.</p>
<p>Other comments</p>	<p>Positive examples and improved metadata practices are seen as important for raising DMP awareness.</p> <p>In some communities, the term “DMP” itself can be a barrier due to existing documentation practices under different names.</p> <p>Several groups are exploring how to align RDMO with other systems.</p> <p>There’s ongoing work to evaluate existing templates and integrate DMPs more meaningfully into workflows.</p>

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